

INTEGRATING ONLINE READING PLATFORMS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION TO FOSTER EMOTIONAL ENGAGEMENT IN ONLINE EXTENSIVE READING

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Abstract. Early childhood education (ECE) is widely recognised as the foundation of children's academic success and overall development. In recent years, there has been an increased interest in integrating up-to-date technological resources and innovative pedagogical approaches to improve the quality of ECE, such as implementing online reading platforms in education, which can result in expanding young learners' extensive reading (ER) on the Internet. This narrative review aims to explore the integration of innovative online reading platforms into ECE to promote emotional engagement in ER on the Internet among elementary school children. Conducting a thorough review of the literature from 45 high-impact indexed articles, this study sheds light on key concepts related to ECE, emotional engagement, online reading platforms, and online extensive reading (OER). Furthermore, it highlights the benefits and potential contributions to early childhood literacy development. The present review concludes that integrating online reading platforms in teaching ER offers educators an opportunity to create engaging environments for emotional engagement with online reading materials. However, teacher guidance and parental oversight are essential for children's interactions or exposure to those platforms, ensuring positive impacts on early literacy growth.

Keywords: Online reading platforms, Emotional Engagement, Reading Interest, Online Extensive Reading, Early childhood education.

Introduction

Synchronous and Asynchronous learning platforms in this turned out to be inevitable in this era of Tesla technology. Digital technologies have become an essential component of contemporary educational practices as they have been widely implemented in the context of early childhood education (ECE), resulting in a paradigm change in education (Chang et al., 2023; Hermansson & Olin-Scheller, 2022; Merritt et al., 2022). Digital technologies play a significant role in ECE, encompassing diverse e-learning methods aimed at fostering the emergent literacy abilities of young learners (Jack & Higgins, 2019; Liu et al., 2024). Likewise, recent research studies emphasise the significance of utilising digital reading platforms for ER in educational settings. Such practices are highlighted for their positive impacts on language acquisition, comprehension skills, reading interest, and attitude (Chowdhury et al., 2024; Habók et al., 2024; Ounissi et al., 2023; Yamashita, 2013).

In recent technological advancements, there has been a noticeable rise in children's engagement with digital devices. This trend aligns with the increasing availability and usage of handheld and mobile gadgets like smartphones and tablets among this age group (Marsh et al., 2015). Children today are immersed in a digital media-saturated environment, with their daily engagement with digital content becoming increasingly common at school and home. This trend is evident across various socio-economic groups, indicating daily and widespread use of interactive and mobile media among children (Marsh et al., 2015). Based on a survey study related to parents of children aged eight and under, almost all respondents (98%) indicated that their young children reside in households equipped with various types of mobile gadgets (Rideout & Robb,

2017). Therefore, Children's exposure to modern technology facilitates their emotional engagement (interest and attitude) with digital devices for educational games and early ER experiences, as well as expanding the availability of children's books in digital forms on portable electronic devices (Bus et al., 2020). Consequently, digitisation has introduced new avenues and opportunities for presenting multimodal text, particularly evident in the accessibility and interactivity of e-books for early readers. Even children with emerging literacy skills can independently engage with e-books, showcasing the inclusive nature of digitization in fostering early literacy development (Dore et al., 2018; López-Escribano et al., 2021).

Research Gap and Rationale for the Study

Children today are deeply immersed in electronic devices, prompting worries about their physical and cognitive growth (Liza et al., 2023). The prevalence of digital gadgets globally in ECE has raised concerns about nowadays reading habits and emotional engagement in reading materials on the Internet, such as online stories in different genres. Despite spending significant time on gadgets, children often lack emotional exposure, precisely in reading extensively on the Internet online. There is a gap in research on how online reading platforms can promote children's emotional engagement, including interest in OER. Even though numerous studies tackled the impact of e-book reading on children's literacy abilities (López-Escribano et al., 2021), there has been minimal research on emotional aspects within the context of online learning, as noted by Zeng et al. (2022), particularly with young children (Thümmeler et al., 2022). Moreover, limited research knowledge exists on the effects of innovative reading platforms on young children's emotional engagement in OER. Additionally, Moreover, there's a lack of research on strategies to guide parents and teachers in promoting extensive online reading and emotional reading habits among young children (Thümmeler et al., 2022). Integrating digital reading platforms into ECE presents an opportunity to address these gaps and foster emotional engagement in OER. This review paper endeavours to bridge these identified gaps by scrutinizing recent literature, presenting some facts, offering numerous online reading platforms (including the researcher's online reading platform), and suggesting recommendations for integrating them. Thus, the aim is to spark children's interest in OER, and therefore, to achieve numerous educational and cultural benefits.

Related Literature

Importance of Digital Technologies in Early Childhood Education

Early childhood education, often abbreviated as ECE, comprises educational initiatives aimed at nurturing children's growth from infancy to approximately age eight, with an emphasis on enhancing cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development among children throughout their early life stages (National Association for the Education of Young Children, n.d.). In ECE, digital technologies have mainly been employed for educational purposes, serving as supporting instruments to enhance and raise standards of learning and teaching, particularly in reading and writing (Beschoner & Hutchison, 2013; Burnett, 2010; Neumann, 2018) as well as problem-solving tasks among young children (Bers et al., 2013, 2014; Murcia et al., 2018). Moreover, instructors can use digital gadgets including scanners, audio devices, cameras, and electronic portfolios to systematically document children's growth (Hooker, 2015; Lyons & Tredwell, 2015). In addition, professional online software programs can facilitate instructional planning and documentation (Dwyer et al., 2019).

The Significance of Online Extensive Reading in Early Childhood Education

Reading scholars have long acknowledged that significant improvements in both receptive and productive skills can occur when learners engage in ER and cultivate a habit of regular reading and improve their linguistics performance (Bamford & Day, 2004; Day & Bamford, 2002; Krashen, 2004; Renandya et al., 2018; Richards & Schmidt, 2002; Yamashita, 2008). The term "Online extensive reading" (OER) denotes various voluntary reading tasks conducted on the internet to foster enjoyment and establish consistent reading practices (Coiro, 2003, 2012). Coiro (2012) emphasized the potential for readers to immerse themselves in an expanded online context, enabling effortless communication and direct engagement within specific online reading settings. Consequently, the world of OER necessitates not just diving into a sea of words for pleasure, but also staying abreast of contemporary digital technology and mastering the art of navigating electronic resources on the web. Similarly, Gilbert (2014) emphasized that thriving in today's digital age requires teachers to impart vital digital literacy skills to their young students, enabling them to navigate online reading materials with proficiency and finesse Arshad, (2023).

Interest in OER as an Emotional Engagement Factor

Emotional engagement is recognized as learners, experiencing positive psychological responses or dedication to specific activities or academic occurrences (Marcus et al., 2021). Skinner and Belmont (1993) defined emotional engagement as learners' emotional responses to the learning environment. Similarly, Fredricks et al. (2004) described EE as encompassing various affective reactions to academic tasks, including happiness, anxiety, interest, and feelings of belonging in educational settings. Interest in OER which refers to learners' enthusiasm for reading beyond school hours, possibly in libraries, in reading corners, or at home (United States Department of Education, 2005) is one of the vital emotional engagement factors. It enhances connections with texts and enriches the reading experience. When readers show interest in digital materials including stories, they become emotionally exposed to deeper understanding, enjoyment, and a desire to keep reading. Hence, emotionally engaged learners are internally driven to actively participate in class and achieve various academic goals (Ounissi et al., 2023). Interest greatly impacts the desire to read and the level of engagement with reading materials (Fox & Alexander, 2003). A study undertaken at a UAE university discovered that opting for intriguing topics fosters learners' interest and encourages ongoing ER despite encountering vocabulary and semantic difficulties (Al Murshidi, 2014). Consequently, a strong interest in reading correlates with impressive academic performance (Oakhill & Petrides, 2007).

Online reading platforms and their role in children's emotional engagement in OER

Online reading platforms encompass the practice of perusing digital texts on the Internet via electronic gadgets such as laptops, smartphones, or e-readers, engaging with diverse digital media like images, videos, and hypertexts. Staying current with technology and possessing proficient skills in Internet search and navigation are essential for this process (Pearson et al., 2013). Numerous online reading platforms (refer to Appendix 1) usually offer free access to their ER libraries, requiring just an email account registration. With just a few clicks, young and adult readers can immerse themselves and indulge in ER on the internet using multiple electronic devices. Thus, those reading platforms (see Appendix 1) provide a wide range of reading genres without any cost barrier and the readers can download the reading materials in various formats. Whether at school or during leisure time, readers can enjoy the enriching experience of OER without limitations, fostering a love for literature and continuous learning. In considering the effect of online reading platforms on children's emotional engagement in reading extensively on the Internet, it's essential to recognise the significance of children's reading abilities in today's

digital landscape. According to Zhang et al. (2022), effective guidance of both parents and teachers plays a pivotal role in promoting positive digital reading habits, yet many parents encounter challenges in effectively engaging with their children in the digital reading realm. Nevertheless, accessible digital reading platforms can serve as valuable tools in fostering meaningful parent-child reading interactions by offering convenient access to content summaries and assisting parents in navigating their children's reading experiences (Zhang et al., 2022).

Conclusion

Teachers play a crucial role in motivating and empowering young learners to explore online reading platforms both in and out of the classroom. Educators should reward and encourage children to delve into online reading materials and share their reading adventures on the Internet, like reading stories, with their peers and families. By creating a supportive environment that fosters OER and encourages discussions about online reading experiences, educators can maximize the benefits of early childhood education. This collaborative approach not only reinforces the importance of online reading skills but also fosters meaningful connections and learning opportunities, enriching the educational journey for young learners. Both instructors and parents should guide their young children in exploring their interests and passions in OER, encouraging them to delve into online reading stories and other reading materials that captivate their imagination. By instilling a love and enjoyment for reading and promoting intrinsic motivation, teachers can accelerate their children's reading fluency and comprehension skills. Moreover, by creating a welcoming atmosphere or supportive environment that stimulates diverse interests and encourages self-directed reading and learning, teachers will possibly empower their young children to take ownership of their reading journey. Therefore, this sets a strong base for their future educational learning and success in ER.

Future Recommendations

To advance and maintain ongoing progress in ECE, it is recommended that educators prioritise the integration of online reading platforms into elementary classroom practices and assignments, aiming to promote OER skills and emotional engagement among young children. Professional development opportunities, such as ICT training should be provided to support teachers in effectively implementing these resources tailored to the needs of ECE. Furthermore, collaboration with parents is crucial to reinforce the importance of OER and encourage their exposure in fostering children's exploration of online reading texts from an early age. Moreover, facilitating discussions among young children about their online reading habits and experiences can improve comprehension and critical thinking skills. Additionally, online reading materials should be appropriate for young readers, match their language level, and should be promoted to meet individual interests and nurture intrinsic motivation. Apart from that, emphasis should also be placed on creating a supportive environment that empowers young children to take ownership of their reading journey through self-directed learning. Thus, evaluating the impact of these strategies on young children's reading fluency, comprehension, and overall literacy skills will achieve future educational practices.

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